

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF ADVANCED COMPOSITE SKULLS FOR THE GM HYBRID III CRASH TEST MANNIKIN

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ABSTRACT

This study compares fabrication techniques for manufacturing reproducible advanced composite skulls for the GM Hybrid III crash test mannikin. Prototype skulls were designed, fabricated, and tested using hand lay-up, resin transfer molding (RTM), and filament winding processes with fiberglass- and graphite-reinforced epoxy. Low-cost methods of prototype production were developed using plaster (external) and sand (internal) molds. Various techniques were incorporated to allow these materials to be used in autoclave curing and for low pressure resin transfer molding without degrading dimensional accuracy. The prototypes were compared for manufacturability, reproducibility, geometric accuracy, and dynamic response. RTM was determined to be the best process for the production of composite skulls. After making process and tooling improvements three advanced prototype skulls were fabricated, evaluated and tested.

KEYWORDS: Mannikin; Skull; Hand Lay-Up; Resin Transfer Molding; Filament Winding

1. INTRODUCTION

Stronger, stiffer, and lighter mannikin skulls which have equivalent inertial and geometric properties to the current aluminum models are needed for modern military aircraft ejection-seat testing. During testing, the skulls on crash test manikins experience acceleration loads as high as 40 to 60 g's in winds up to 1130 kph (700 mph) [1,2]. These propulsive and aerodynamic forces have been responsible for exciting the natural frequencies of the aluminum skulls, interfering with data acquisition. The tailorable stiffness and inherent damping properties of advanced composite materials enable circumvention of this ringing interference. Advanced composite materials also result in lighter skulls which allow more advanced instrumentation to be used without exceeding weight limitations.

This paper summarizes the design and development of advanced composite skulls for aircraft ejection seat testing. The research involved an evaluation of alternative fabrication techniques for manufacturing reproducible advanced composite skulls for the GM Hybrid III crash test mannikin. As part of this research, three prototype skulls were designed, fabricated, and evaluated using hand lay-up, resin transfer molding (RTM), and filament winding processes with fiberglass- and graphite-reinforced epoxy. Based on an evaluation of the skulls, RTM was selected for further development. Three advanced prototype RTM skulls were then fabricated, tested, and delivered to the Naval Air Development Center (NADC) for final evaluation and testing. The basic geometry of the skulls is shown in Figure 1 [3,4].

2. PRELIMINARY PROTOTYPE COMPOSITE SKULLS

2.1 Process Selection Several fabrication alternatives were initially considered for this project including wet hand lay-up, prepreg hand lay-up, spray-up, preform molding, filament winding, injection molding, and resin transfer molding. The potential of each of these methods was considered based on the given project requirements, which did not specify a

fabrication technique. The advantages and disadvantages of each process were examined, resulting in the selection of hand lay-up, resin transfer molding, and filament winding for further development [5,6,7].

FIGURE 1. Geometry and coordinate system of GM Hybrid III mannikin skull

The process for fabricating skulls using hand lay-up involves combining reinforcing fabric and matrix material in an external mold. A split-skull design is necessary for external molding in order to have access to the skull interior during lay-up. After the part is laid-up, the molds with the skull halves inside are autoclave cured [6,7].

The process of resin transfer molding a skull consists of placing a reinforcing fiber preform between internal and external molds and injecting resin. The vacuum-assisted resin injection method was selected. This process uses vacuum to draw the resin into the preform, eliminating the need for expensive tooling necessary in high pressure RTM. After the preform is injected, the resin is cured by heating the mold assembly in an oven, after which the skull is demolded and machined [6].

Filament winding a skull entails winding pre-preg tow around a mandrel to produce the basic skull shape. Since the shape is rather complex, the chin could not be filament wound along with the rest of the skull. Instead, the chin was hand-laid up in an external mold. The skull core and chin were vacuum bagged and autoclaved cured using this external mold, which allowed autoclave pressure to further consolidate the resulting co-cured joint [5,6,7].

2.2 Materials Selection Two fiberglass fabrics from Hexcel were used in the hand lay-up and RTM portions of this project: an 8-harness satin weave fabric (style 4581) and a bi-axial weave tooling fabric (style 4533). A graphite 8-harness satin fabric (style 584) was used, along with the 8-harness satin fiberglass, for the advanced prototype skulls. The resin system used for hand lay-up was Shell Epon DPL-862, which has low toxicity, good mechanical properties and easy processing characteristics. Two resin systems, Shell Epon 9400 (preliminary prototype) and Shell Epon DPL-862 (advanced prototype), were selected for RTM because of their processability, good mechanical properties, and ready availability. All resins were mixed and processed according to the manufacturer's specifications.

2.3 Tooling Design and Fabrication The molds for fabricating the skulls needed to be low cost and simple to produce; thus, plaster external molds were selected for the preliminary prototypes. The advantages of low cost and simplified processing far outweighed the limited durability of plaster tooling. Sand was chosen for internal mold construction for all

phases of the project. To prepare an internal mold, the sand was combined with a water soluble binder (Plastilease 512B) in a fiberglass mold and oven cured [8,9].

In order to produce external molds, an aluminum GM Hybrid III skull was obtained from NADC for use as a pattern. Two basic mold designs were employed: one for hand lay-up and the other for RTM and filament winding. The hand lay-up molds were made with the unmodified GM Hybrid III skull shape, while a chin extension was installed to produce the RTM/filament winding mold. A parting plate was attached to the pattern to allow a two-piece mold to be produced. A mold box was constructed from plexiglass, with a plaster inlet hole in one side and the parting plate on the other side. The mold box was sealed to the parting plate with RTV silicone sealant to prevent wet plaster from leaking out. The mold box and parting plate were coated with a silicone-based wax as a release agent and assembled in the desired configuration using RTV silicone sealant. Bondex Hobby Modeling Plaster was mixed according to the manufacturer's directions and poured into the mold box. After 30 minutes, the mold box was removed and the pattern was pulled from the part. The mold was allowed to dry for several days before being coated with high temperature enamel (hand lay-up, filament winding) or epoxy sealant (RTM). Coating the mold with release agent completed the mold-making process [8,9].

The internal mold had to be smaller than the external mold by the desired thickness of the part being produced. To accomplish this, a two-piece fiberglass mold of the skull without the chin was constructed using wet hand lay-up to the desired thickness. This mold was then used to form the finished internal molds/mandrels. To start mold production, sand was mixed in a five-to-one ratio by weight with Plastilease 512B. The mixture was poured into the molds and compacted with a hammer. The molds were heated in an oven to 149°C (300°F) for 3 hours. After curing, the parts were removed from the mold and trimmed with a file. The internal mold halves were glued together using white glue and allowed to dry. For filament winding, the mold was mounted on a mandrel rod by drilling a hole into the mold and adhesively bonding the rod in place. Finally, the internal molds/mandrels were coated with RTV silicone sealant, which filled the imperfections and sealed the mandrel against resin infiltration [9].

2.4 Preliminary Prototype Skull Design and Fabrication

2.4.1 Hand Lay-Up: Fabrication of the hand lay-up skull started with the production and sealing of the external molds. The reinforcing materials were then marked and cut using pre-designed patterns for consistency. The next phase was to mix the resin with Shell Epon Curing Agent W in a 26:1 ratio by weight. The resin was debulked by drawing a 95×10^{-2} bar (28 in Hg) vacuum on the container of resin for several hours, which eliminated air bubbles incurred during mixing. The external molds were coated with release agents and wet lay-up proceeded for one half of the skull at a time. The front mold half was first coated with resin, using a small brush to work the resin into the mold details. Layers of fiberglass cloth and resin were then placed in the mold in alternating layers and resulting wrinkles were removed.

After half of the plies were in place, the assembly was vacuum bagged and debulked for several hours to eliminate air bubbles induced during lay-up. After all the plies were laid up, flange plates were installed on the mold halves. Flange plates were used to obtain a smooth, accurate flange to bond the skull halves together. To install the flange plates, reinforcing material was rolled toward the center of the mold until none projected away from the parting surface. The flange plate was carefully positioned and firmly fastened to the mold using tape.

After applying the cure materials, the part was vacuum bagged and autoclave cured with a standard temperature cycle, using a one-hour hold at 120°C (250°F) and two-hour hold at 177°C (350°F). A pressure of 172 KPa (25 psi) was applied and a 93×10^{-2} bar (27.5 in. Hg.) vacuum was drawn. After curing, the vacuum bag and curing materials were removed and the skull halves were demolded. The skull halves were then bonded together with Newport Adhesive's NB-101 film adhesive. The film adhesive was trimmed to fit the flange area and the parts were clamped together using alignment

marks and a small alignment jig. The assembly was placed in an oven and cured at 149°C (300°F). Finally, the skull was finished by wet sanding with fine sandpaper.

2.4.2 Resin Transfer Molding: RTM skull fabrication began with marking and cutting fiberglass fabric using patterns, as in the hand lay-up process. The preform construction was started by hand stitching five plies to the internal mold using thermoplastic fiber. Next, plies were laid into the external mold halves and the fabric-covered internal mold was inserted into the back external mold. When the internal plies were snug, the front mold half was mated to the back mold half to ensure that the mold halves fit together properly. Then, the back half was removed and both halves were prepared for final assembly. Extra material and loose fibers that projected out of the mold halves were carefully removed with a razor knife. Any remaining loose fibers were pushed between the internal and external mold, to permit proper sealing. The desired outcome was for the fibers to form a smooth transition between the two mold halves, with the five internal mold plies firmly connecting the two skull halves. Prior to the final mold closing, the adjoining mold faces were cleaned with acetone and a bead of high temperature RTV silicone sealant was applied to the front mold half. The silicone was allowed to set-up for 10 minutes, after which the mold halves were assembled for the last time and more silicone was applied to fill any gaps between the molds. The molds were then clamped together and placed in an air-tight vacuum bag. Shell Epon 9400 resin was mixed in a 100-to-31.5 ratio by weight with Shell Epon 9450 hardener. The resin was weighed, mixed, and debulked in a similar manner to the hand lay-up resin.

The RTM process equipment was then moved into the autoclave chamber. The equipment consisted of the vacuum-bagged mold containing the preform, a metal container of resin, a resin trap, a hot plate, four C-clamps and assorted high temperature tubing. The mold was set up on concrete blocks at an angle of approximately 15° to keep the resin flowing uphill to prevent dry pockets. The resin was injected in the bottom of the mold and drawn out of the top, allowing gravity to assist in completely filling the mold. The hot plate was placed on the autoclave floor, keeping the resin supply lower than the mold, to prevent air bubbles from becoming trapped in the hoses. The container of resin was placed on the hot plate which maintained a resin temperature of 54-66°C (130-150°F) during resin injection. The resin trap was hung from the top of the autoclave to allow at least two feet of hose between the trap and mold assembly. Connecting hoses were attached with hose clamps: the resin inlet hose connected the can of resin to the bottom of the mold, the resin outlet hose connected the top of the mold to the resin trap inlet, and an autoclave vacuum hose connected the autoclave vacuum source to the resin trap vacuum port. A C-clamp was used to control resin flow by pinching the resin inlet hose.

The RTM process was initiated by firmly clamping the resin inlet hose and applying full vacuum to the part. After five minutes, the vacuum source valve was closed manually. During the next five minutes, the mold was checked for leaks by examining the vacuum bag. The vacuum source valve was then opened and full vacuum was applied for another five minutes to ensure that no air remained in the preform. The pressure on the inlet hose C-clamp was then slowly released until a satisfactory resin flow was established. The flow was estimated at a rate of approximately 11 ml/min. This flow rate was maintained for approximately 90 minutes, until nearly all of the resin had been used. At this point, the resin inlet and outlet hoses were closed completely using C-clamps. The system vacuum was released and the resin outlet hose was fully opened for one hour, to allow atmospheric pressure to force more resin back into the mold. The resin outlet hose was then closed with two C-clamps and the excess hose (beyond the C-clamps) on the inlet and outlet sides was removed. The hot plate, resin trap and assorted hardware were removed from the autoclave and the cure cycle was started. The cure cycle maintained a temperature of 177°C (350°F) for two hours. No vacuum or pressure were used during the RTM cure cycle. After curing, the mold was removed from the autoclave, debugged, and de-molded.

2.4.3 Filament Winding: The filament-wound skull employed only the front half of the external mold and a removable sand mandrel. Prepreg tape was used to reinforce the top, bottom, and back of the skull. The first winding

segment consisted of two layers of circumferential (90°) plies around the middle of the skull. Then, the initial plies of unidirectional prepreg were installed. These consisted of 15 plies laid on the skull base in a $[0_3/90_3/0_3/90_3/0_3]$ stacking sequence, 8 plies laid on the skull top in a $[0_3/90_2/0_3]$ stacking sequence, and 6 plies laid on the back of the skull in a $[0_2/90_2/0_2]$ stacking sequence. The bottom and back plies used the same pattern for simplicity, while the top required an additional pattern. The patterns were designed to yield a small overlap between the prepreg plies and the 90° filament-wound segment. This overlap allowed the plies to adhere to the tow already in place. Next, a $\pm 40^\circ$ helical pattern was wound, followed by another pair of 90° plies. Six prepreg reinforcing strips were then installed in a $[0_2/90_2/0_2]$ stacking sequence to strengthen the chin-joining region of the skull. This region was not receiving adequate coverage from the tow due to the asymmetry of the mandrel. Once the reinforcing strips were in place, another pair of 90° plies was wound, followed by another set of $\pm 40^\circ$ helical plies. The filament winding was completed by winding a single 90° ply around the middle of the skull. Although a symmetric lay-up would have been preferred, at this point winding was stopped to prevent excessive material buildup, which would have prevented the skull from fitting into the pre-constructed external mold.

The skull was now ready for joining to the pre-prep chin, part of which was previously hand laid into the external mold using four large axial (0°) chin plies extending over the face area, to help hold the chin to the skull by providing a continuous fiber link. The filament-wound skull was then placed into the mold and forced down until the entire face touched the bottom of the mold to obtain good external geometric accuracy. With the skull in the mold, six 2.5 cm. (1 in.) by 5 cm. (2 in.) strips of prepreg were rolled into tubes and pushed into the gap at the intersection of the skull floor and chin. Partial plies, which did not extend into the face area to avoid excessive material buildup, were then added to construct the rest of the chin. The partial plies were extended up to the floor region of the skull to help tie the chin and floor firmly together. These plies were alternated with base plies which ran along the exterior of the skull floor. The stacking sequence used in the chin was $[0_8/90_2/0_4/90_2/0_4/90_2/0_8]$ for a total of 30 plies, while the stacking sequence of the base plies was $[0_3/90_3/0_3]$ for a total of 9 plies. The chin plies and base plies were alternated to increase the floor to chin bond strength. After the lay-up was completed, cure materials were applied and the skull was vacuum-bagged and cured. After curing, the vacuum bag and curing materials were cut away and the skull was de-molded and machined.

2.5 Evaluation of Preliminary Prototype Composite Skulls Evaluation of the prototype composite skulls was separated into two primary categories: the first involved an evaluation of the processes as related to the production of skulls, the second focussed on an evaluation of the current and potential quality of the prototype composite skulls. The process evaluations covered both advantages and disadvantages, while the skull quality evaluations included an assessment of the shape, surface finish, structural quality, and fabrication issues. These parameters were examined to determine the suitability of each process to the production of skulls. The ratings are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1: QUALITY OF PROTOTYPE SKULLS.

CHARACTERISTIC	FABRICATION PROCESS		
	Hand Lay-up	RTM	Filament-Wound
Shape	Very Good	Excellent	Good
Surface Finish	Good	Fair	Good
Structural Quality	Good	Very Good	Very Good

TABLE 2: ULTIMATE POTENTIAL QUALITY OF SKULL PROCESSES.

CHARACTERISTIC	FABRICATION PROCESS		
	Hand Lay-up	RTM	Filament-Wound
Shape	Very Good	Excellent	Very Good
Surface Finish	Excellent	Excellent	Very Good
Structural Quality	Very Good	Very Good	Excellent
Reproducibility	Good	Excellent	Excellent
Overall Quality	Very Good	Excellent	Very Good

3. ADVANCED PROTOTYPE SKULLS

3.1 Process Selection Although filament winding ultimately promises the highest structural performance, the process requires significant development. Conversely, the RTM process required little additional development to allow production of relatively high quality skulls. For this reason, RTM was chosen for production of the three high quality skulls.

3.2 Selected Process Testing Before proceeding, static and dynamic tests were performed on the original aluminum skull and the prototype fiberglass RTM skull. These tests were designed to determine what modifications were necessary in the advanced prototype RTM skulls. Prior to testing, the RTM skull was cut in half along the mold parting line to remove the sand mandrel, which had hardened after absorbing resin during the injection process. The two skull halves were then bonded together with epoxy film adhesive to facilitate testing. Both the aluminum and RTM skulls were weighed and the natural frequencies were determined from the dynamic response to an impact. The RTM prototype was also tested for dynamic strength in the z-direction. A more detailed description of these tests is provided in the following sections.

3.2.1 Natural Frequency Testing: The lowest few natural frequencies were determined with the skulls mounted on the neck fixture. The fixture was clamped to a massive frame structure and the skull was instrumented with one PCB Piezotronics, Inc. (PCB) Model 303A03 accelerometer coupled to a PCB AC line power supply, Model 482A. The accelerometer was alternated between three locations, shown in Figure 2, while the skull was struck with an impact hammer using a measured amount of force (~ 620 N). The impact hammer was a Bruel & Kjaer (B & K) Model 8202 with a mass of 280 g, and used a plastic tip. The signal from the impact hammer was sent through a B & K line drive amplifier, Type 2644, which was powered by a B & K line drive power supply, Type 2813. The data was acquired with a Nicolet oscilloscope at a rate of one point every 20 microseconds. Duplicate tests were performed at each location on each skull. Both the impulse and accelerometer data were collected and analyzed. A Fast Fourier Transform was performed on the accelerometer data to isolate the dominant natural frequencies for the aluminum skull, as well as the RTM preliminary prototype. These results indicate that the dominant frequency in the aluminum skull is 1400 Hz, while the preliminary prototype RTM skull has dominant frequencies at 1225 Hz and 1350 Hz. The lower frequency was used as a baseline for refinements in the advanced prototype RTM skull design.

3.2.2 Destructive Compression Testing: The third test was to statically load the RTM skull in compression to simulate a dynamic load of 60 g. A dynamic load factor of 2 (most severe case) was used to convert the dynamic load to a static equivalent [10]. The fully-instrumented skull weight was assumed to be 44 N (10 lb.), which yields a desired static structural strength of 5340 N (1200 lb).

The RTM skull was mounted to the base and supported by a custom-built rail fixture. The skull was instrumented with three Micro-Measurements CEA-06-125UR-120 strain rosettes, located at points in areas considered to be high stress

regions. Two rubber pads were placed on the crown of the skull to distribute the load and prevent localized cracking. Strain rosette 1 was placed 2.5 cm (1 in.) from the base, in the z-direction, and 2.5 cm (1 in.) from the back, in the y-direction. Rosette 2 was also placed 2.5 cm (1 in.) from the base, in the z-direction, but was located 8.9 cm (3.5 in.) from the skull back, in the y-direction. Rosette 3 was placed 12.7 cm (5 in.) from the bottom of the chin, in the z-direction, and was located directly along the skull's line of symmetry.

FIGURE 2. Accelerometer and strain rosette locations

The skull was loaded at 0.25 cm/min (0.1 in/min) using a Tinius-Olsen universal testing machine. The tests were performed in two parts: first to 5340 N (1200 lb.) and then to failure. After the first test, the data revealed that the skull had strained very little. No cracking was heard or other failure observed during the first test, so the skull was reloaded. Upon reaching 10.7 kN (2400 lb.) of compressive load, the skull emitted a loud pop, and the test was stopped. The bond joining the two halves of the RTM skull had cracked, although the fiberglass portions of the skull had not sustained any visible damage. The highest strain recorded during testing was approximately 400 microstrain, which is far below the amount of strain needed to fail the composite. The rosettes may not have measured the maximum strain present in the skull, but a good representation of the strain state in the skull was determined.

3.3 Process Refinement An increased crown thickness of 0.76 cm (0.3 in) and a new reinforcement combination of approximately 70% carbon and 30% fiberglass fabric (by volume) were selected for the advanced prototype RTM skulls. These fabrication improvements increased the natural frequency by increasing the structural stiffness of the high quality RTM skulls.

Along with an increase in stiffness, the advanced prototype RTM skulls required a better surface finish. The most cost-effective way of producing a better surface finish and an accurate external shape is to use composite tooling. Properly constructed tooling can be reused many times, eliminating the labor required to make a separate plaster mold for each skull. In light of these facts, fiberglass tooling was selected for the advanced prototype RTM skulls. The tooling was made from 20 plies of fiberglass-reinforced epoxy and successfully used for all of the advanced prototype RTM skulls. The overall design of the new tooling was patterned after the plaster tooling set [6,8].

3.4 Advanced Prototype Skull and Tooling Fabrication The fiberglass/epoxy tooling was produced using a hand lay-up process similar to lay-up of the preliminary prototype skull. Also, the size of the internal sand molds was reduced to yield thicker skulls, and the mold was coated with silicone to prevent resin infiltration. This technique was successfully demonstrated during fabrication of the filament-wound preliminary prototype skull. The advanced prototype RTM skulls were produced using the same process as the preliminary prototype skulls. The only significant change was a switch to Shell

FIGURE 3. Front and side views of highest quality RTM skull

Epon DPL-862 resin, with corresponding changes in the injection procedure and cure cycle. The highest quality RTM skull is shown in Figure 3.

3.5 Testing and Evaluation of Advanced Prototype RTM Skulls

3.5.1 Mass and Geometry Measurement: The weights of the advanced prototype skulls after machining are shown in Table 3. The variation in skull weights was caused by the resin loss problem incurred during processing and is not an inherent flaw in the process. The skulls were also measured after machining, revealing only very small variations in geometry. These were not considered an issue in the advanced prototype RTM skulls. Estimates of the average resin content and fiber volume fraction for each skull are also listed in Table 3. These were determined by calculating the mass and volume of reinforcement material. The remaining skull mass was then assumed to be resin. Although these are only estimates, they still provide reasonable approximations of the average fiber/resin ratios for each skull.

TABLE 3: MASS PROPERTIES OF RTM SKULLS AFTER MACHINING.

Skull Type	Skull Mass (g)	Resin Content (%)	Fiber Volume Fraction (%)
Aluminum Skull	1590	---	---
Preliminary Prototype RTM Skull	940	---	---
Advanced Prototype RTM Skull 1	888	41	43
Advanced Prototype RTM Skull 2	922	38	46
Advanced Prototype RTM Skull 3	984	41	43

3.5.2 Natural Frequency Testing: The same series of dynamic testing was performed on the three advanced prototype RTM skulls as on the aluminum and the preliminary prototype RTM skulls, amounting to six tests per skull. The advanced prototype skulls were obviously stiffer and had an audibly higher natural frequency than the preliminary prototype RTM skull, suggesting that the neck or clamping fixture was responsible for the measured frequencies. To isolate the effect of the base on the measured frequencies, the skulls were hung by a thin string and tested without the base. The string, which was approximately one meter (three feet) long, was attached to a massive frame structure at one end. The other end of the string was tied to the base of the skull. These tests were performed for two configurations on each of the advanced prototype RTM skulls, as well as the original aluminum skull. For the first configuration, the accelerometer was mounted in accelerometer location 1, and impact hammer location 1 was used. For the second configuration, the accelerometer was mounted in location 3, and impact hammer location 2 was used. Unfortunately this test could not be performed for the RTM prototype skull since its frequencies were altered when the bond joint failed during compression testing.

The results, shown in Figures 4 and 5, clearly indicate that some of the lowest frequencies obtained from the advanced prototype RTM skulls are higher than those obtained with the aluminum skull. However, not all of the frequencies are increased significantly. This could be due to factors such as the shape of the skull, limited thickness of some sections of the skull (such as fitting the chin into the latex skin), and the presence of extra material in the aluminum skull (which reinforces the rear crown area). This reinforced area, which is used as a hook mount for the test mannikin, could have a significant effect on the natural frequencies of the aluminum skull.

Another parameter of interest is the amount of damping offered by the composite skulls. This data, shown in Figures 5 and 6, is not easily compared, since the large difference in mass between the aluminum and RTM skulls affects the dynamic response. The lighter RTM skulls reach a much higher magnitude of vibration (acceleration) since they have less inertia (mass) than the aluminum skulls. However, relative to the initial magnitude, the rate at which the magnitude is reduced shows that the RTM skulls have much higher damping than the aluminum skulls, as expected.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a high quality, advanced prototype composite skull has been fabricated from a combination of fiberglass- and graphite- reinforced epoxy, using resin transfer molding. The natural frequencies of the advanced prototype skulls have been increased from those of the preliminary prototype RTM skull. The frequencies are also nearly the same or higher than those of the original aluminum skull. There are, however, several other factors which affect the lowest few natural frequencies; such as boundary conditions, skull shape, and skull mass. A more detailed analysis of the dynamic response should be performed to fully understand these effects. Finally, the damping effect of the composite material has been shown to be significant, and will reduce the amount of undesirable vibration the skulls experience during ejection testing.

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FIGURE 4. FFT of aluminum skull with free boundary conditions

FIGURE 5. FFT of advanced prototype RTM skull 3 with free boundary conditions

FIGURE 6. Accelerometer data from aluminum skull with clamped boundary conditions

FIGURE 7. Accelerometer data from advanced prototype RTM skull 3 with clamped boundary conditions